

Cryptocurrencies – A Curse or Blessing?

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ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Jan Malkus studied theoretical computer science at the Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany, and specialised in corporate management. For many years he has taken a strong interest in computer science's technical challenges, especially those concerning how to advance in business such technological innovations as artificial intelligence and blockchain technology. His long-term success as a serial entrepreneur is in part due to his passionate commitment to achieve sustainable, commercial benefits from the use of technologies in business across processes, practices and systems.

“The new realities of our time are based on facts that we need to bring back to our consciousness. This awareness will open up new possibilities for us and the following generations to reflect on humanity, to correct mistakes and to master new challenges. One of our tasks is to support and position real people as best as possible in a virtual world, to ensure security and to protect personal rights.”

For more information on the author, visit www.janmalkus.com

PREFACE

Few topics in business are as controversial as cryptocurrencies: this is despite their use occurring in a much smaller financial market environment than other assets. A key reason for this involves two questions of understanding: What are cryptocurrencies? And, how do they work? Stating that they are digital assets on a blockchain doesn't make them accessible to most people beyond knowing this basic information. Are they simply units of account, as defined by BaFin (2020)?; are they commodities, as described by several renowned authors?; or are they nothing more than financial fraud?, according to James Dimon, CEO and Chairman of JPMorgan Chase & Co. Bank, who denounced them publicly in September 2017 (FAZ, 2017).

Irrespective of definition, the facts remain: cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin have a total stock market value of around 2 trillion USD, which roughly corresponds to that of the US giant Apple (June 2021). At the same time, Bitcoin has a market capitalisation that makes it one of the ten largest assets in the world (coinmarketcap, 2021). Combined, however, all cryptocurrencies represent less than 0.001% of global financial assets. Nevertheless, these small electronic configurations make the financial world shudder. This makes no sense, given the magnitude of the mainstream financial markets and their assets when compared with cryptocurrencies. So, what is this all really about? I contend that it is based on nothing less than the fear of the global financial economy collapsing.

“We don't know where the money comes from. It is there or not there - mostly not there.”

(Kurt Tucholsky, 1931)

Cryptocurrencies have the potential to make all central banks in the world insignificant. That sounds frightening to many, especially in times of a global pandemic: who would act as a saviour and subsidise hopelessly indebted nations if no central bank activates its money press at short notice to print new money?

As numerous examples worldwide show, the value of a payment unit - here, meaning currency, in the classic sense - depends on the trust in its central bank or nation-state(s). The times in which a tangible equivalent always secured a currency are over: if you want to buy goods tomorrow, you must create a basis of trust. As is well known, money is on the street: in the course of the Covid-19 pandemic, global economic output has almost halved, while the money supply has increased significantly - all with little or no inflation.

The possibility of nearly infinite fundraising in connection with the holistic control of the flow of money by the central banks is the most powerful financial process in the world. And it is precisely this system that is threatened by cryptocurrencies. For this reason, cryptocurrencies have a bad reputation among those vested in maintaining the status quo in the world of politics, among central banks and within regulatory authorities.

Although all cryptocurrencies can be considered as a unit, as stated earlier, they are not (yet) economically significant. Still, they are already being recognised in many ways as superior to conventional currencies and, in time, could replace them. This merits further explanation and context.

Already we have seen some noteworthy developments occur in rapid succession, including:

- In El Salvador, the Bitcoin cryptocurrency is already a standard means of payment
- Sweden appears to be the first European nation that will implement its own cryptocurrency. The Swedish government has already announced it will establish the e-Krona as an electronic parallel currency alongside its physical krona between 2022 and 2023 (Lindenberg & Ummelas, 2020). Sweden has therefore recognised the prevailing trend
- In 2024, the European Central Bank wants to launch its digital Euro on the market
- Meanwhile, other central banks appear alarmed as they worry about staying ahead in the great game of power and money?

This is all incredibly exciting, and there's so much at stake. Just consider, what will the establishment do to prevent itself from being disempowered, and how will people's cryptocurrencies usage behaviour change? These matters are examined in more detail below.

CRYPTOCURRENCIES – A DEFINITION AND OVERVIEW

According to Wikipedia (2021), cryptocurrencies are digital means of payment based on cryptographic tools such as blockchains and digital signatures. However, they are unlike currencies in the traditional sense. This is because, as payment systems, cryptocurrencies promise independence, decentralisation and, therefore, security. Accordingly, cryptocurrencies enable digital payment transactions without central authorities such as banks. This is done with the help of decentralised data management and transmission protocols that are cryptographically encrypted. The possession of a cryptological key represents the ownership of credit.

Furthermore, the credit - which is also signed cryptologically - is mapped in a joint accounting system in a separate storage form, known as the blockchain. As a rule, currency units are generated jointly by the entire system in a predetermined number. In the same way, the production rate is also specified in advance and published or limited by a cryptographic type of generation.

One of the most important differences to conventional means of payment is that with most cryptocurrencies, a single party cannot accelerate, impair or abuse the production of currency units in any way. Cryptocurrencies, therefore, do not need central banks and are not (yet) subject to any authority or other organisation.

Due to their decentralised structure - in contrast to monies issued by central banks - cryptocurrencies usually don't have a single point of failure that could endanger or even manipulate the currency. However, this must be put into perspective. Some cryptocurrencies are produced centrally by owner-managed, private, profit-orientated companies. For example, Ripple Labs holds 80% of the new issues of the Ripple cryptocurrency and distributes it according to its own rules.

Cryptocurrencies are fiat money - just like the monies predominantly issued by central banks today. They are created out of nothing and only have use-value, not intrinsic value. Such value only arises through its acceptance between trading partners (e.g., payers, recipients), which results from its possible uses and resulting advantages.

Bitcoin, the first cryptocurrency, was publicly traded in 2009. In Germany in 2013, the federal government recognised this cryptocurrency legally and for tax purposes as a unit of account and a type of private money for use in multilateral clearing circles (Münzer, undated). Germany's Federal Financial Supervisory Authority (BaFin) classifies Bitcoin as a unit of value comparable to foreign exchange. Therefore, the relatively new recognised crypto money is neither legal tender nor e-money, foreign exchange or foreign money. Switzerland as a state doesn't recognise it as means of payment in many regions. Still, in the canton of Zug, for example, it is possible to pay one's tax with Bitcoin. From a tax point of view, established cryptocurrencies are often treated as securities.

THE CRYPTO LANDSCAPE IN 2021

Cryptocurrencies

Der russische Präsident Vladimir Putin, die Fastfood-Kette Burger King, das US-Unternehmen Kodak und natürlich der ehemalige US-Präsident Donald Trump haben etwas gemeinsam: eine eigene Kryptowährung! In den letzten 10 Jahren hat sich die Anzahl von Kryptowährungen weltweit vervielfacht – Tausende sind mittlerweile im Umlauf und es kommen ständig neue hinzu. Diese virtuellen Währungen bilden folglich einen wachsenden lukrativen Markt, der die Aufmerksamkeit der Anlegenden auf sich zieht.

According to coinmarketcap.com, the ten most successful cryptocurrencies as of September 2021 are:

#	Name	Price	Market Capitalization	Volume (24 hours)	Circulating Supply
1	Bitcoin	€47,746.61	€901,190,226,701	€33,183,357,112 692,343 BTC	18,802,575 BTC
2	Ethereum	€3,416.83	€402,499,628,140	€25,794,941,284 7,519,373 ETH	117,330,951 ETH
3	Cardano	€0.8442	€52,504,419,446	€35,728,135,964 42,315,851,938 USDT	32,145,348,141 ADA
4	Binance Coin	€473.13	€79,550,201,708	€2,407,236,498 5,087,927 BNB	153,432,897 BNB
5	Theter	€1.00	€65,521,354,245	€82,894,220,508 82,855,280,523 USDT	65,490,575,253 USDT
6	XRP	€1.14	€53,473,678,321	€4,074,092,152 3,543,812,926 XRP	46,513,604,835 XRP
7	Dogecoin	€0.2784	€36,597,933,878	€1,504,958,900 5,190,423,494 DOGE	131,087,333,601 DOGE
8	Solana	€0.8442	€22,414,725,680	€1,746,930,995 2,069,155,857 USDC	26,549,165,971 USDC
9	Polkadot	€30.07	€29,868,811,015	€3,865,425,444 127,806,032 DOT	987,579,315 DOT
10	USD Coin	€1.00	€27,453,940,822	€3,192,977,915 3,192,564,485 USDC	27,450,386,054 USDC

Infobox:

Cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin and Ethereum have recorded a significant track record and increase in value in recent years, despite market slumps. However, lesser-known cryptocurrencies are considered to be much more speculative and unpredictable (coinmarketcap, 2021).

Infobox:

The PutinCoin and Whoppercoin belong to a category of cryptocurrencies that are more absurd than their potential as an investment. However, this shows how unique different types of cryptocurrencies can be (Marvin, 2018).

Crypto exchanges

If you want to invest in cryptocurrencies, you have the option of using various crypto exchanges, crypto brokers, decentralised exchanges or peer-to-peer exchanges. They offer trading or direct purchase in different ways and with different functions for different coins and tokens, which can be transferred to private wallet addresses, so they are protected from access by third parties.

Currently, the ten most successful crypto exchanges as of September 2021, according to coinmarketcap.com, are:

#	Name	Exchange Score	Volume (24 hours)	Weekly Visits	#Markets
1	Binance	9.8	\$31,223,671,289 ▲ 51.67%	26,967,204	1408
2	Coinbase Exchange	9.0	\$5,804,720,335 ▲ 100.94%	2,915,085	287
3	Kraken	8.5	\$1,429,588,858 ▲ 79.08%	1,973,798	336
4	KuCoin	8.4	\$1,997,882,948 ▲ 52.73%	1,446,259	860
5	Huobi Global	8.4	\$6,330,536,045 ▲ 58.65%	907,660	943
6	FTX	8.3	\$2,789,212,689 ▲ 60.74%	2,415,690	506
7	Binance.US	8.2	\$1,178,60,074 ▲ 93.25%	759,273	283
8	Bitfinex	8.1	\$975,176,267 ▲ 92.23%	804,618	310
9	Gate.io	7.9	\$659,295,011 ▲ 54.94%	2,087,496	1490
10	Bithumb	7.9	\$1,144,036,406 ▲ 17.37%	606,261	255

Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs) and Security Token Offerings (STOs)

According to Wikipedia (2021), an Initial Coin Offering (ICO) is typically an unregulated method of crowd investing used by companies whose business model is based on cryptocurrencies. With this method of raising capital for the first time, cryptocurrencies avoid the strictly regulated process required by venture capitalists, banks and stock exchanges.

Projekt	Stage	Start	End	Goal
DRIFE DRF	IDO ends in 2 hours left	6. Aug. 2021	6. Aug. 2021	\$150,000
Gamestarter GAME	IEO ends in 13 hours left	6. Aug. 2021	7. Aug. 2021	\$50,000
AST.finance DRF OKExChain	IDO ends in 2 days left	6. Aug. 2021	8. Aug. 2021	--
Cardence.io \$CRDN Binance Smart Chain	ICO ends in 13 days left	20. Juli 2021	20. Aug. 2021	\$100,000
Cardence.io \$CRDN Binance Smart Chain	IEO ends in 13 days left	20. Juli 2021	20. Aug. 2021	\$100,000
Base Reward Token BRT Binance Smart Chain	IDO ends in 1 month left	25. Juli 2021	15. Sept. 2021	\$300,000

In the case of the issue of so-called security tokens, national securities laws apply so that Security Token Offerings (STOs) are subject to similarly strict regulation, comparable to regulated mutual funds. In an ICO, a portion of a newly issued cryptocurrency is sold to investors in exchange for state-issued currencies or other cryptocurrencies. On the other hand, an STO describes a public sale of values, rights, or obligations that are mapped using digital tokens.

Token	Market Cap	Price	Change %	Volume 24 h	Exchange	Price Trend
Overstock OSTKO	\$290,605,000	\$66.50	0%	\$99,750	tZERO	
INX Limited INX	\$216,441,628	\$1.75	0.57%	\$44,803	INX Securities	
tZero TZROP	\$136,907,836	\$6.58	0%	\$57,878	tZERO	
Blockchain Capital BCAP	\$87,799,550	\$12.50	38.89%	\$38	INX Securities	
FirstShot Centers LLC FST	\$38,303,999	\$1.89	1.61%	\$17,002	CryptoSX	
Science SC12	\$31,839,894	\$1.95	0%	\$137	INX Securities	

The technical basis for both types (ICO and STO) is provided by blockchain technology, which is used to issue tokens and validate subsequent transactions. Currently, a wide variety of assets such as B. Securities, real estate, loans and company shares are tokenised. The advantages that result from tokenisation are transparency, higher liquidity and better efficiency compared to traditional investments. In addition, investors or holders of the tokens have similar rights towards the issuer as with conventional securities, e.g., B. Entitlements to dividend-like payments, participation rights or interest payments (Wikipedia, 2021).

Cryptocurrencies and their development prospects

Interesting developments in the crypto sector can be seen again and again, especially in Switzerland. The Swiss canton of Zug is considered the European centre of blockchain and crypto companies. Since the beginning of 2021, the tax authority there has enabled taxpayers and companies to pay tax bills up to a maximum amount of 100,000 Swiss Francs in the Blockchain and Ethereum cryptocurrencies.

The associated partnership between the canton and Bitcoin Suisse, the crypto-financial service provider, enables a smooth process: the virtual currency is exchanged for Swiss Francs at the current exchange rate and forwarded to the administrative apparatus. Moreover, the system's functionality is perfect, reported Zug's finance director Heinz Tännler in February 2021, meaning that regular use of the service can be forecast in the future (Bürgi, 2021).

Of course, the crypto business is picking up speed just as quickly in the USA. For example, Wyoming - which to many outsiders is more likely to evoke the image of the "Wild West Way of Life", with cowboys on horseback and large herds of cattle - claims the title of the most crypto-friendly state in the United States and opens its doors to all types of crypto business models.

Infobox: Wyoming - How it all began

In 2017, Caitlin Long, the former CEO of Morgan Stanley, the investment firm, arranged for her alma mater, the University of Wyoming, to make a donation in the form of Bitcoin. However, this was not possible due to restrictive state laws. Long refused to accept this and successfully sued to change the crypto regulations in Wyoming. Subsequently, Wyoming has developed into an oasis for crypto business models, offering attractive conditions and support from its Wyoming Blockchain Taskforce, which Caitlin Long was appointed to head by the Wyoming governor's office in 2018 (Matthews, 2021).

The many opportunities the state offers crypto companies confirm the success of this approach: two of the largest crypto companies - Ripple, valued at \$10 billion in December 2019, and Kraken, valued at \$4 billion in February 2019 - have already settled in the state and many more will undoubtedly follow (Botella, 2021).

It is particularly exciting to see the speed at which draft laws can be introduced in favour of cryptocurrencies. For example, the laws passed in Wyoming in 2018 and 2019 defined the handling of digital assets in commercial law. In addition, they created a legal basis for so-called "smart contracts" for the first time: contracts that are automatically executed via computer code on the blockchain.

Infobox: Examples of newly enacted Wyoming laws

- Crypto investors can easily form a limited liability company.
- Investors residing in another state can hold digital assets in Wyoming for legal purposes.
- Institutional investors are given the opportunity to have direct ownership of digital assets held by a custodian bank.
- Legal status is granted to decentralised autonomous organisations as well as communities with members who work with blockchain technology.

Since the start of 2021, a similar development has been evident in the US city of Miami. The city has been looking for a long time to find ways to attract technology companies and new business models to Florida – including financial and technology-promoting companies. In addition, South Florida has followed the strategies of New York City and San Francisco to foster conceptual framework conditions and enable Miami to become an innovation hub. Accordingly, the city is pursuing stringent plans to make its infrastructure as crypto-friendly as possible (Huang, 2021).

These developments clearly show how cryptocurrencies are gradually becoming more and more established in broad sections of the population: administrative zones, cities and state structures are all recognising the potential opportunities for doing business in this way.

An overview: further developments, milestones and cuts in 2021

As already noted, cryptocurrencies have positioned themselves broadly in the last decade. They are now enjoying the recognition of a large audience. As a result, their status is no longer that of a niche interest. It is now increasingly the norm to be aware of a growing number of business opportunities and positive discussions involving cryptocurrencies.

Infobox: Miami takes action to use cryptocurrencies

- City employees should be given the opportunity to have their salaries paid in Bitcoin.
- Local fees or taxes could be paid in Bitcoin or another cryptocurrency.
- The city's treasury would invest part of its investment capital in cryptocurrencies - private investors would have the opportunity to participate (Levin & Smith, 2021).

1. The increasing spread of cryptocurrencies

According to Handelsblatt (2021), the Bundesbank has noted that only 350,000 transactions with cryptocurrencies are made worldwide each day, compared to 77 million transfers, direct debits and card payments in Germany alone.

2. PayPal accepts payments with cryptocurrencies

With the new Checkout with Crypto function, users in the USA can easily sell parts of their cryptocurrency balances within their PayPal account and exchange them for traditional currencies (Spiegel, 2021).

3. ECB announces digital Euro

Even if this is an attack on the crypto business, this is an important signpost: the European Central Bank is starting a three-year test phase, and citizens are expected to be able to use wallets or apps from the banks on which they can store digital Euros.

4. German Federal Ministry of Finance is looking for possible solutions

The German federal government has also recognised the phenomenon. In June 2021, the Federal Ministry of Finance published the draft for a paper that should regulate individual questions about virtual currencies and tokens (BMF, 2021).

5. China is attacking cryptocurrencies

In June 2021, China closed data centres to clamp down on cryptocurrencies: the government instructed local banks and Alipay, the payment platform, to stop offering services for trading cryptocurrencies (FAZ, 2021).

CRYPTOMINING - THE SYSTEM BEHIND CRYPTOCURRENCIES

Cryptocurrency mining describes a process in which the users' transactions are verified and added to the public blockchain ledger, i.e., the blockchain equivalent of the cash book. This mining process is also responsible for implementing new coins in the existing offer already in circulation. Accordingly, mining is a key process that enables cryptocurrencies to function as a decentralised peer-to-peer network without a third central authority (Binance Academy, 2018).

The concept

A miner is a type of node in the network that records, collects and systematically organises transactions in blocks. Whenever a transaction is made, it is checked for validity by all network nodes. The miner nodes then collect these transactions from the storage pool and combine them into a block (known as a candidate block).

The Process

1. Hashing

Hashing is the process of converting a string of characters into a (usually) shorter, numeric value or key with a fixed length. So, the first step in mining a block is to hash each transaction that is individually taken from the storage pool. However, before this process begins, the miner node adds a transaction to send itself a mining reward (a block reward). This transaction, in turn, is known as the Coinbase transaction, where coins are created out of nothing. In most cases, this is the famous first transaction recorded in a new block.

2. Merkle Tree organisation

After each transaction has been hashed, the hashes are organised in a so-called Merkle Tree. It is formed by organising the various transaction hashes into pairs and then they are hashed. The resulting outputs are then also organised in pairs and hashed again. This process is repeated until the top of the Merkle Tree is reached.

3. Root-hash

After reaching the root hash, this is then inserted into the header, i.e., the block's header, together with the previous block's hash and a random number called Nonce. This block header is then hashed, producing output based on the elements root hash, the hash of the previous block and the Nonce, and a few other parameters. The resulting output is the block hash and serves as the identifier of the newly generated block (a candidate block).

4. Check for validity

To be considered valid, the output - meaning, the block hash - must be less than a specific target value determined by the protocol. In other words, the block hash must start with a certain number of zeros.

5. Target value

The target value - also known as the hashing difficulty - is periodically adjusted by the protocol to ensure that the rate at which new blocks are created remains constant and proportional to

the hashing performance of the network. Therefore, every time new miners join the network and competition increases, this hashing difficulty logically increases and prevents the average block time from decreasing. However, suppose miners decide to leave the network. In that case, the hashing difficulty decreases and the block time is kept constant, although the network requires less computing power.

Therefore, the mining process requires miners to hash the block header repeatedly by going through the Nonces until someone in the network finally generates a valid block hash. Then, when a valid hash is found, the first miner node - the founder node - sends the block to the network. Lastly, all other network nodes finally check whether the respective hash is valid, add the block to their copy of the blockchain and proceed to mine the next block (bitpanda, undated).

Infobox: China is fighting against cryptomining

It is estimated that 65% to 75% of the world's bitcoin mining occurs in China, and mainly in four Chinese provinces: Xinjiang, Inner Mongolia, Sichuan and Yunnan. The Chinese government is now taking rigorous action against this. According to the Chinese media, almost 600 Bitcoin miners in the northern municipality of Tianjin were confiscated for electricity theft and countless systems were shut down in June 2021. As a result, the price of the oldest cryptocurrency rushed to the bottom (FAZ, 2021).

CRYPTOMINING AND ITS ENERGY CONSUMPTION

In 2018, Forbes dubbed cryptomining the nail in the coffin of climate change (BR, 2021). The reason for this was the issue of the much-discussed electricity consumption required for cryptomining. The more our attention has become focused on cryptocurrencies, the more its associated energy production has also come into focus, creating conflicting opinions across the globe. Without a doubt, in most cases, digital production is energy-intensive. But actually, how much energy does cryptomining consume?

The Cambridge Bitcoin Electricity Consumption Index of Cambridge University showed an annual energy consumption of almost 115 terawatt-hours (TWh) in June 2021. However, the data from the Digiconomist portal was slightly higher, with a value of 126 TWh per year. Furthermore, Dutch scientists noted in 2018 that a Bitcoin transaction, for example, requires a similar energy consumption to that used by 80,000 credit card transactions: and this is a value that can now be rated even higher (BR, 2021).

Infobox: Electricity consumption comparison: Germany vs. China

Germany has an annual electricity consumption of 517 TWh. Using a country comparison with China, it becomes clear what a massive difference there is between two modern states in terms of energy use. China has an annual electricity consumption of around 6,510 TWh (BR, 2021).

The Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung describes the effects of a single crypto transaction even more drastically: the electricity consumption is as high as that of an average American household in 23 days. Put another way: the carbon footprint is as huge as streaming 54,000 hours of internet videos. (FAZ, 2021).

Why does it require such high energy consumption?

For computers to mine a cryptocurrency, they must perform a complex series of calculations that require significant computing power. The technology involved entails the use

of countless computers worldwide working at their performance limit. In principle, the power needed for this could be done with regenerative energy to reduce consumption. However, another critical issue is the location of the energy source: the mining location is decisive because the reality is that two-thirds of all cryptominers are in Asian countries, where energy is primarily generated from coal-fired power plants. Furthermore, the more popular the crypto trend becomes, the bigger the requirements for computers, data centres and server farms, all of which use a large amount of energy. For example, the continuous block mining cycle gives people all over the world an incentive to mine Bitcoin. Since this can provide a reliable source of income, some of these people are ruthlessly willing to run energy-guzzling machines. Over

the years, this has caused the total energy consumption of the Bitcoin network to reach epic proportions as the price of the currency reaches new highs. As a result, the entire Bitcoin network now consumes more energy than some countries.

States also play a role here. Take Kazakhstan, for example. It produces Bitcoin in encrypted form with state money, and the government is known to set different priorities over and above the use of clean electricity. Another influencing factor is the exchange rate of currencies such as Dollars and Euros. For prospecting, the higher the difference between the current price and the operating costs, the more profit can be made (Wiget, 2021). In simple terms: the higher the price, the higher the energy consumption. So, clearly, it is important to consider environmentally-friendly alternatives – and this is something about which all the experts agree.

Bitcoin Energy Consumption

Energy Consumption by Country (Annualized TWh)

Location	Power consumption (megawatts)	% of surveyed facilities	Carbon intensity (gCO2eq/kWh)
China	111	47.60	711
Georgia	60	25.80	231
United States	27	11.60	489
Canada	18	7.70	158
Sweden	10	4.3	13
Iceland	5	2.1	0
Estonia	2	0.90	793
Total/Weighed Average	233	100.00	475

Is there an alternative?

The Proof of Work system was the first consensus algorithm that proved itself in blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies. However, this procedure is not the only option. Others are less known because they lack big players like Bitcoin that have an extensive media reach. Nonetheless, more energy-efficient algorithms such as Proof of Stake have been developed in recent years.

In the proof of stake procedure, the system requires a deposit in advance, which entitles the user to verify blocks. Anyone who violates this loses their deposit. This does not affect the actual security of the blocks or their encryption. However, it is determined in advance who can verify the respective block instead of letting the computing power alone decide this. That would mean immense savings on energy use. For this reason, the energy consumption of the proof of stake is significantly lower than that of the proof of work. It's incredible to consider that switching to the proof of stake system could save 99.95% of the energy volume currently required to operate a proof of work-based system (Reetz, 2019).

Another alternative is the Proof of Selection procedure. The standard mining requirements are unnecessary for this method, so the energy needed can be significantly reduced. Moreover, with proof of selection, block publication and transaction rights are granted without centralised coordination processes or other authorities. Therefore, the speed of proof of selection is significant and works without time restrictions to create blocks while also being scalable since the number of selected nodes can be increased (Hargrave, 2018).

Processes will need to be improved and established for future use. Large providers such as Bitcoin or Ethereum could also retrofit them and, if necessary, change their procedures. If not, users would likely focus on other cryptocurrencies with improved blockchain technologies.

HOW SECURE IS THE ELECTRONIC WALLET?

Cryptocurrencies are stored in a virtual purse: the so-called wallet. If you want to trade with a cryptocurrency, you must use a wallet. The wallet works based on asymmetric cryptography with two different digital keys - a public and a secret, private key. However, the actual currencies only exist on the blockchain. Therefore, the wallets per se do not store the virtual money but instead manage the public and private keys required to access the cryptocurrency. In brief, wallets allow coins to be held, sent, and received.

As is so often the case, whenever there is something of value, there is also someone who wants to enrich themselves. Therefore, a cautionary note must be made regarding criminal activities in this area, such as attempted fraud.

Infobox: Security gaps don't occur in the blockchain

Security gaps in a crypto wallet usually don't arise due to the blockchain technology or the cryptocurrencies themselves. The problem arises with the users, the people: The security risk is posed by the efforts of hackers and online fraudsters to access users' sensitive data via their smartphones, computers and laptops as well as via their use of the websites through which cryptocurrencies are bought and sold. Such data includes the wallet and its keys stored by users on their devices and their website use to buy and sell cryptocurrencies. Therefore, improving data security is a fundamental priority across all applications and aspects of cryptocurrency use (bsi, undated).

Storage systems and their weak points

There are different types of wallets or storage systems, all of which work in their own way, and they can also have different security vulnerabilities. The following list gives an overview.

1. Hot Wallet

Hot wallets can usually be called up via a browser or have a constant connection to the internet. Crypto values held via trading platforms are also classed in this category. However, large amounts should not be stored on hot wallets: the risk of falling victim to a hacker is high.

2. Cold Wallet

A cold wallet is a hardware or paper wallet that has no connection to the internet and is encrypted. Consequently, it offers more protection against theft than a hot wallet. The hardware wallet is

usually a device that stores the private keys of crypto assets, which are mostly encrypted. Examples include B. with a USB stick (the simplest form), Trezor, Ledger, and Bitbox. On the other hand, the paper wallet is sometimes the safest way to store crypto assets because the public address and the private key are written down or printed (Crook, undated).

Other security concepts**1. Secure internet connection**

Using a VPN connection instead of public networks offers better protection against digital crime and data theft.

2. Protection through accounts at regulated crypto exchanges

Using a regulated crypto exchange or a similar provider usually requires a KYC identity check when registering, which helps to improve security against attempted fraud.

3. Multiple wallets

The allocation of daily transactions to different wallets disguises the actual activities and prevents systematic identification by third parties.

4. Protect/secure personal devices

Whenever and for whatever reason we are online, we should consider the following as essential parts of our digital lives: antivirus programmes, strict firewall settings, regular password changes, the deletion of phishing emails without ever opening them, and the implementation of software updates. The importance of these activities also applies when dealing with cryptocurrencies.

THE BIGGEST CRYPTO HACK EVER

Probably the most recent and noteworthy example of security issues for crypto interfaces was a spectacular hacker attack in August 2021 in the Decentralised Finance (DeFi) area. DeFi is the term used to describe financial offers with decentralised control instead of centralised, and in which intervening entities - such as banks and brokers - are omitted. The idea behind this form of control is that crypto entrepreneurs can replicate traditional financial instruments in a decentralised architecture – and do so outside the control and regulation of companies and governments.

In the words of Alex Pack, managing partner of Dragonfly Capital, a \$100 million crypto fund, “The goal of DeFi is to reconstruct the financial system for the whole world in an open, permissionless manner.”

As money laundering and misuse allegations have increased in centrally controlled systems, the demand for purely decentralised applications has become even more relevant (Kauflin, 2019). A considerable effort is being made to achieve this vision, but new systems always harbour a risk of fraud. According to Cybertrace, the blockchain forensics team, the total of crypto thefts, hacks and frauds amounted to \$681 million by the end of July 2021. Although this number is lower than the highs of previous years, a breakdown of the types of theft and fraud here confirms a trend observed at the beginning of the last quarter: DeFi-related crime continues to increase from quarter to quarter (Clegg et al., 2021).

In particular, two types of DeFi crimes have been identified. One type is the hacking of a DeFi protocol, which is also known as a ‘rug pull’. A rug pull occurs when crypto developers abandon a project and steal their investors’ money. However, another type comprises the majority of DeFi crimes in 2021: hacks carried out by outsiders, which accounted for \$361 million or 76% of DeFi-related crimes. The remaining 24% were rug pulls, which were over \$113 million at the end of July 2021 (Chavez-Dreyfuss, 2021).

The attack on Poly Network: a massive coup

On 10 August 2021, a hacker used a smart contract from Poly Network, the crypto-asset exchange platform, to exchange recipient addresses. As a result, he stole over \$600 million. The company, Tether - with an unregulated cryptocurrency going by the same name - then froze 33

million USDT, which the hacker had transferred there, at the request of Poly Network. The hacker attack represented a new dimension in the possibilities of cybercrime - and the media worldwide published news about the mega coup. One such news story, as reported by the German media, stated:

“Initially, Poly Network reported that the hacker had returned units of the Ether cryptocurrency, worth \$4.6 million, \$252 million in so-called Binance tokens and \$85 million in Polygon. Ethers with a value of \$268 million remain open. The platform later tweeted that all ether values had been transferred.”

How was this hack possible?

In 2021, SlowMist, the Chinese crypto security company, summarised the complex sequence of events for the general public:

1. The attacker carefully constructed an operation in the source chain to modify the keeper of the target chain
2. The attacker then exchanged keeper data
3. He then used the replaced address to sign the process and sent it to the EthCrossChainManager for verification
4. The verification took place successfully
5. The hacker transferred assets to different wallets.

The vulnerability

The process described above sounds quite simple, and the associated security gap was just as simple as it was fatal. The hacker found out that a Poly Network smart contract offered a function that everyone could conduct a cross-chain transaction independently, even if they weren't a Poly Network client. In the last step of this function, a connection to the target smart contract was established. At this point, Poly Network failed to determine or regulate which smart contracts could now be called. This enabled the hacker to get into the EthCrossChainData smart contract and access a list with all public keys (keys) to verify transaction data. The hacker only had to prepare and feed in the correct data set to include the keys he had created himself in the list of verification keys, thereby enabling him to verify his transactions and transfer assets worth over \$600 million (Fichter, 2021).

Ultimately, it was a sophisticated exploit for an inadequately designed smart contract, which now primarily affects Poly Network's users. Moreover, there is no evidence that the Poly Network code has ever been tested (JJ, 2021). This confirms once again that security gaps arise in connection with cryptocurrencies, especially within interfaces. Poly Network also recognised this and publicly congratulated the hacker on his success on Twitter, thanking him for the later return of the assets:

„Dear Hacker, Thank You! We are ready for a new journey. Poly Network Team“

(@polynetwork2, 2021)

Infobox: The Robin Hood of crypto hacking?

According to The Verge (2021), the US online portal, the hacker paid back the stolen millions in full after two weeks. He announced in encrypted form that he had only stolen the money to keep it safe. The hacker even made a brief apology to Poly Network's users: "SORRY FOR THE INCONVENIENCE! IT MUST BE ONE OF THE MOST WILD ADVENTURES IN OUR LIVES." However, many argue that because he could not have made the stolen money simply disappear, his justification for stealing the money remains controversial. Meanwhile, Poly Network, with a wink of the eye, offered the hacker the opportunity to act as the company's chief security advisor and stressed that no prosecution would be initiated. This was also questionable, because the company's customers suffered financial damage and presumably, therefore, they would have preferred the hacker to have been prosecuted. How the whole thing will develop remains to be seen as the transparency of blockchain technology can make it a difficult process to reimburse stolen funds.

OUTLOOK AND OPPORTUNITIES

Cryptocurrencies have developed into a global phenomenon. They also trigger many concerns, worries, and great opportunities. The same can be said for their associated technology and social change, especially regarding traditional financial systems. According to an online article from Stanford University, proponents of crypto financial platforms argue that they are inherently trustworthy systems - they are not directly tied to any nation-state, government, or corporation. Therefore, their sovereignty makes them superior to traditional physical currencies (Stanford, undated).

At the moment, however, this is not (entirely) correct: cryptocurrencies are still dependent on an appropriate infrastructure. For example, the Chinese government could fundamentally change cryptocurrencies by imposing their will on the data miners who keep them running - as it did recently with the shutdown of several crypto farms, discussed earlier.

Infobox: As in many areas, the scope and scale of use is important

The future of cryptocurrencies depends a lot on their reach. So it is not surprising that global companies such as PayPal, Tesla and many more are integrating cryptocurrencies into their business models and are also becoming more (moneytoday.ch, undated).

However, it makes sense to look to the future because that is what's truly exciting. We are in an early phase of the crypto revolution, so defining the status quo as a long-term fixed evaluation would be pointless. As soon as blockchain-based business models are recognised, omnipresent in the mass market and within our consumer communities, entire industries will change – comparable to what happened at the start of the Noughties when e-commerce took hold.

Above all, the blockchain, i.e., the technology behind cryptocurrencies, has the greatest potential here. As a result, coins will continue to develop new and even more efficient transmission and storage systems. According to Forbes (2021), blockchain is predicted to become one of the most important pillars of the digital society.

It is evident that in the future, cryptocurrencies could replace any conventional currency. The decentralised system enables every user to participate in creating virtual money by buying or selling an electronic currency. Central banks and other entities such as brokers are not required

in any way, and during a transaction period of 48 hours, they don't have the opportunity to speculate with their users' money. This is because every transaction is recorded and confirmed by the community, not by a central authority.

Infobox: Things keep moving

Another interesting crypto project for investors is NEO, the Chinese cryptocurrency. In addition to the smart contracts, NEO brings with it digital assets and a digital identity. In addition to services provided by smart contracts, property such as real estate or proof of identity such as ID cards can be stored on the blockchain (Mittermeier, 2021).

One of the most exciting prospects is that cryptocurrencies will change the understanding of property within society because ownership will become more transparent. Cashless payment is a method already well-established, and it will be made much more secure in the future. Moreover, the total assets of a person and a company can be precisely traced using blockchain technology without being impaired in data protection or identity security. The political dimension is also evident: how much better could the practice of democracy work when there's only the slightest risk of electoral fraud? Accordingly, blockchain will simplify and improve our lives in many areas of society, and - in financial matters - cryptocurrencies provide an exciting outlook of what is to come.

Without a doubt, crypto Euros, Pounds and Francs will come, which will be issued by central banks as stablecoin - stable in the exchange rate - at a ratio of 1:1 to the physical currency. But bear in mind that central banks are not required for this. Consider as an example that Teller Limited in the USA created a stablecoin as the equivalent of the US Dollar. The coin is called Tether, has the USDT abbreviation, and can be exchanged at any time as a means of payment for real US Dollars - at a ratio of 1:1. So now the question arises if the government of the United States offers its own stablecoin, which one would its citizens prefer: the state-controlled stablecoin or instead the private-sector stablecoin not controlled by any authority?

CONCLUSION

After reflection on all the investigations, inventories and evaluations, it remains clear to me: even before the battle has begun, the winner of the first big battle has already been decided: cryptocurrencies will replace all conventional physical currencies. It is entirely open to conjecture, however, how this will happen exactly. Who would instigate the initial spark to trigger this, and which technical solution would enable it?

One thing, however, is already certain. Newer technologies and verification measures will be established that are not nearly as energy-intensive as today's processing and technical processes relating to Bitcoin. And it should be clear to many that, with such a nascent technology, not everything can be fully developed and refined at once. So we can expect that blockchain will be renewed, protocols will be improved and newer, more secure, cheaper and more efficient solutions will follow. New actors and players will rise or fall in the battle for supremacy in crypto-related matters. Meanwhile, even if central banks won't act promptly, no one should rush to write them off. Be it the Central Bank of China or another central bank, many interested parties are already preparing to launch a state-owned cryptocurrency.

I think the consequence of this is already apparent. All conventional currencies will be replaced as exact copies on the blockchain. That sounds almost boring: apart from a new look, everything stays the same – nothing would be better for politicians and central banks. However, the opposite will be the case: it will never be easier to print money than it will be in the future. The most exciting thing about doing so is that it will still be legal - at least according to current case law. The stablecoins of the central banks will compete with some cryptocurrencies. This is precisely what central banks are not used to - they have lived in a non-competitive environment since their inception, making them indolent. Central banks were created to ensure stability, control the money supply and regulate interest rates and inflation. They were not created to be innovative or promote innovation. They therefore lack the know-how, processes and instruments to prepare for the upcoming competition.

That is why I'm confident that one of the most exciting times in the financial industry is still ahead of us. Nothing will stay as it is. In future, all current securitisations of values - bonds, futures, currencies, commodities, stocks, real estate - will be combined with intelligent, blockchain-secured solutions. A number of new technical solutions will offer evermore advan-

tages over previous systems. And new solutions will create new players. As already mentioned in my preface, all physical and cryptocurrencies worldwide are primarily about trust. After all, why can the US print money almost indefinitely even though the country is heavily indebted? It's because we all trust that the US will always service its interest on all debts. And while old debts will continue to be replaced by new debts, as happens in states around the world, history has already shown the fragility of this system. For example, during the financial crisis of 2008 and 2009, Greece would inevitably have slipped into insolvency without massive support from the European Union. Billions of new Euros were printed for this purpose. However, in the future, the European Central Bank (ECB) would have to issue new Euros as stablecoins in the same ratio. This has to find acceptance among the users (the citizens). But there can also be other Euro/stablecoins not controlled by the ECB, which can have other advantages (technically better, faster, safer, cheaper or simply more popular).

There are no limits to the imagination, so there are bound to be millions of solutions for blockchain technology and crypto assets worldwide. Just consider as one example: why shouldn't the global coffee giant Starbucks have its own cryptocurrency - the Starbucks Coin - which would bring several advantages for Starbucks customers? At the same time, this would mean that the company would have all the addresses of all Starbucks wallets. Accordingly, Starbucks could distribute gifts to these wallets with the help of Free Air Drops to motivate its customers time and again to return to one of the company's many stores and buy products there. It would be a perfect retention tool and an excellent customer loyalty measure. At the same time, all purchases would be settled directly at Starbucks without requiring any bank or credit card fees. There are many other such examples of exciting applications. We can also expect they will all share certain benefits: they will be more modern, flexible and intelligent than today's solutions.

A new world paradigm is being created that would transform all our financial systems. Today's monopolists - the world's central banks – would not only then face new peers, but they would also be thrown into a competition for the first time. To continue to play any role of significance, participants will have to reposition themselves completely. Authority will most likely be redistributed, and new market participants will be introduced to deliver exciting new solutions for an engaging, new and global financial market environment.

I am very optimistic about these changes. Meanwhile, the status quo is not viable as it will continue to create distance between people and consumers. This isn't ethical, nor is it in keeping with our times. Frankly, almost all entrepreneurs have had at one time or another to experience the unfounded arrogance of big banks or many quasi-monopolistic ones in their everyday business life. This will be completely different in the future. My prognosis for the future of the financial market is that if you don't adapt, you won't survive. New solutions will be much more efficient, so that we will be able to process millions of transactions with high-performance systems while no longer requiring today's complex, large and expensive infrastructures. We can expect highly automated, cloud-based services with as little infrastructure as possible (asset-light). These will be superior to conventional systems and set the new standard, and cryptocurrencies will play a vital role. They will become an indispensable part of the financial market of the future.

There remains only one question left to consider: cryptocurrencies – a curse or blessing?

Certainly, they're a curse for those who fundamentally oppose any innovation and only recognise dangers or risks in new possibilities. On the other hand, they're a blessing for those of us who would welcome the inauguration of a more modern, secure world. With cryptocurrencies, counterfeit money could potentially become a crime of the past, and terrorist financing and large-scale money laundering could be made impossible thanks to cryptocurrencies. Moreover, new possibilities are opening up to make global payment transactions more efficient.

I look forward to this future.

Responsible for content

The paper only reflects the author's opinion and point of view. It was created with the greatest possible care. Regardless of this, the author rejects any liability for contained errors or facts and their correlations.

IMPRINT

Author	Jan Malkus
Image sources	Jan Malkus, unsplash.com
Figures	All figures were created internally. (Data from: coinmarketcap.com)
Contact	Jan Malkus, info@janmalkus.com

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Acheson, N. (2020, November 1). *Crypto Long & Short: Wyoming Is Crypto's 'Wild West,' Which Is Exactly What We Need*. <https://www.coindesk.com/crypto-regulation-custody-wild-west>

Bitcoin: Warum die Kryptowährung so viel Strom verbraucht (2021, June 18). BR. <https://www.br.de/nachrichten/wirtschaft/bitcoin-warum-die-kryptowaehrung-so-viel-strom-verbraucht,SaaWkfl>

Botella, E. (2021, June 28). *Wyoming Wants to Be the Crypto Capital of the U.S.* <https://slate.com/technology/2021/06/wyoming-cryptocurrency-laws.html>

Blockchain sicher gestalten: Konzepte, Anforderungen, Bewertungen (n. D.) Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik. https://www.bsi.bund.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/BSI/Krypto/Blockchain_Analyse.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3

Bürgi, M. (2021, February 25). *Steuern bezahlen mit Krypto-Geld: So geht das im Kanton Zug*. [https://www.handelszeitung.ch/geld/steuern-bezahlen-mit-krypto-geld-so-geht-das-im-kanton-zug-\(buergi\)](https://www.handelszeitung.ch/geld/steuern-bezahlen-mit-krypto-geld-so-geht-das-im-kanton-zug-(buergi))

Chavez-Dreyfuss (2021, August 1). *„DeFi“ crime hits record high in first 7 months of 2021-CipherTrace*. <https://www.reuters.com/technology/defi-crime-hits-record-high-first-7-months-2021-ciphertrace-2021-08-10/>

China setzt Bitcoin weiter unter Druck (2021, June 21). FAZ. <https://www.faz.net/aktuell/finanzen/digital-bezahlen/bitcoin-china-verschaerft-seinen-kurs-gegen-kryptowaehrungen-17400023.html>

Clegg et al (2021) *Cryptocurrency Crime and Anti-Money Laundering Report*. Cyphertrace <https://ciphertrace.com/cryptocurrency-crime-and-anti-money-laundering-report-august-2021/>

Coinmarketcap (n. D.) *Liste von Kryptoexchanges*. <https://coinmarketcap.com/de/rankings>

Crook, J. (2019, February 26). *The Differences Between Cold, Warm, and Hot Storage*. www.ctera.com/company/blog/differences-hot-warm-cold-file-storage/

Fehr, M. (2021, June 29). *Was Bitcoin-Anleger in der Steuererklärung beachten müssen*. <https://www.faz.net/aktuell/finanzen/was-bitcoin-anleger-in-der-steuererklaerung-beachten-muessen-17407687.html>

Fichter, K. @kelvinfichter. (2021, August 11). *Statement zum Poly-Network-Fall*. [Tweet]. <https://twitter.com/kelvinfichter/status/1425217046636371969>

Haar, J. (2021, 15. Juli). *The 10 Most Popular Cryptocurrencies, and What You Should Know About Each Before You Invest*. NextAdvisor In Partnership with TIME. <https://time.com/nextadvisor/investing/cryptocurrency/types-of-cryptocurrency/>

Hargrave, J. (2018, November 28) . *Proof of Selection: A Better Alternative to Proof of Work*. <https://jhargrave.medium.com/proof-of-selection-a-better-alternative-to-proof-of-work-917aa44e4b9a>

Holtermann, F. (2017, September 10). *Bitcoins bitte! Die Zukunft des Geldes hat begonnen*. <https://www.handelsblatt.com/finanzen/maerkte/devisen-rohstoffe/bitcoins-bitte-die-zukunft-des-geldes-hat-begonnen/20270118.html>

Huang, R. (2021, February 1). *Miami's Mayor Leads The Charge To Bring Bitcoin To America's Largest Cities*. <https://forbes.com/sites/rogerhuang/2021/02/01/miamis-mayor-leads-the-charge-to-bring-bitcoin-to-americas-largest-cities/>

Initial Coin Offering. (2021, July 23). in Wikipedia. https://de.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Initial_Coin_Offering&oldid=214141006

J, J. (2021, August 12). *Poly Network Suffers Largest Crypto Hack Ever Recorded*. <https://ciphertrace.com/poly-network-suffers-largest-crypto-hack-ever-recorded/>

- Kauflin, J. (2019, April 26) *Why Everyone In Crypto Is Talking About DeFi*.
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/jeffkauflin/2019/04/26/why-everyone-in-crypto-is-talking-about-defi/>
- Krypto-Hacker zahlt wohl alles zurück*. (2021, August 12). tagesschau.
<https://www.tagesschau.de/wirtschaft/krypto-raub-101.html>
- Kryptowährung. (2021, September 3. In Wikipedia. <https://de.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Kryptow%C3%A4hrung&oldid=215283498>
- Levin, J. & Smith, M. (2021, February 11). *Miami Pushes Crypto With Proposal to Pay Workers in Bitcoin*. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2021-02-11/miami-mayor-pushes-crypto-with-offer-to-pay-workers-in-bitcoin>
- Lindeberg, R., & Ummelas, O. (2020, December 11). *Sweden Explores Moving to a Digital Currency*. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2020-12-11/sweden-explores-the-feasibility-of-moving-to-a-digital-currency>
- Locke, T. (2021, June 11). *You could be leaving your crypto wallet open to hackers—here's how to protect it*. <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/06/11/tips-to-help-keep-your-crypto-wallet-secure.html>
- Marvin, R. (2018, February 6) *23 Weird, Gimmicky, Straight-Up Silly Cryptocurrencies*.
<https://www.pcmag.com/news/23-weird-gimmicky-straight-up-silly-cryptocurrencies>
- Matthews, C. (2021, April 23). *How Wyoming became the promised land for bitcoin investors*.
<https://www.marketwatch.com/story/how-wyoming-became-the-promised-land-for-bitcoin-investors-11619201182>
- Mittermeier, A. (2021, August 3). *NEO: Was bringt Chinas Kryptowährung für Anleger?*
<https://www.gevestor.de/finanzwissen/kryptowaehrungen/neo-was-bringt-chinas-kryptowaehrung-fuer-anleger-821781.html>
- moneytoday.ch (n. A, n. D.) *Kryptowährungen*.
<https://www.moneytoday.ch/lexikon/kryptowaehrungen/>
- Münzer, J. (2013, December 19). *Bitcoins: Aufsichtliche Bewertung und Risiken für Nutzer*. BaFin. https://www.bafin.de/SharedDocs/Veroeffentlichungen/DE/Fachartikel/2014/fa_bj_1401_bitcoins.html
- Newman, L. (2020, August 5). *Cryptocurrency Hardware Wallets Can Get Hacked Too*.
<https://www.wired.com/story/cryptocurrency-hardware-wallets-can-get-hacked-too/>
- Papasabbas, L. (n. D.). *„Wir befinden uns in der Frühphase der Krypto-Evolution“*. <https://www.zukunftsinstitut.de/artikel/wir-befinden-uns-in-der-fruehphase-der-krypto-evolution-inter-view/>
- PayPal führt Bezahlen mit Kryptowährungen ein*. (2021, March 3). Spiegel.
<https://www.spiegel.de/netzwelt/apps/bitcoin-paypal-fuehrt-bezahlen-mit-kryptowaehrungen-ein-a-0eeaae39-8485-4f21-aa1b-f2bcd89f2709>
- Poly Network hacker gave back more than \$600 million in stolen crypto. (2021, August 23). The Verge. <https://www.theverge.com/2021/8/23/22638087/poly-network-600-million-stolen-crypto-hack-restored-defi>
- Reetz, F. (2019, March 1). *Blockchain & das Klima – Warum die nationale Blockchain- Strategie Innovations- und Klimapolitik zusammenbringen sollte*. Stiftung Neue Verantwortung.
https://www.stiftung-nv.de/sites/default/files/blockchain_und_das_klima.pdf
- Siedenbiedel, C. (2021, June 14). *Die EZB macht den Weg frei für den digitalen Euro*.
<https://www.faz.net/aktuell/finanzen/die-ezb-macht-den-weg-frei-fuer-den-digitalen-euro-17436959.html>
- SlowMist (o. A.) (2021, August 11). *The Analysis and Q&A Of Poly Network Being Hacked*.
<https://slowmist.medium.com/the-analysis-and-q-a-of-poly-network-being-hacked-8112a35beb39>
- Swigunski, M. (2021, April 17) *How Cryptocurrency Will Transform The Future Business Forever*. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/mikeswigunski/2021/04/17/how-cryptocurrency-will-transform-the-future-business-forever/?sh=777fab524368>

Was ist Bitcoin Mining und wie funktioniert es? (n. D.).bitpanda.

<https://www.bitpanda.com/academy/de/lektionen/wie-kann-ich-kryptowahrungen-sicher-verwahren/>

What Is Cryptocurrency Mining? (2018, December 6). Binance. <https://academy.binance.com/en/articles/what-is-cryptocurrency-mining>

What Does the Future Hold for Cryptocurrency? (n. A., n. D.) Stanford online. <https://online.stanford.edu/future-for-cryptocurrency>

Wiget, Y. (2021, February 12). *Bitcoin verbraucht jetzt mehr Strom als die Schweiz und Österreich zusammen.* <https://www.derbund.ch/bitcoin-verbraucht-jetzt-mehr-strom-als-die-schweiz-und-oesterreich-zusammen-431918446142>